

THE LEVEL OF INSTILLING THE CONCEPTS OF NATIONAL VALUES INTO THE CHILD'S MIND DURING THE DAILY EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS.

TDPU in the name of Nizomi

"Pedagogy and psychology of preschool education"

department teacher **H.U. Rizayeva**

moxira0405@mail.ru

Annotation: *In this article, you can see an analysis of the daily activities of preschool educational organizations, that is, the work they do during the day, and by what methods the concepts of national value are instilled in children.*

Keywords: *frontal, value, national, development centers, activity, education, program, educational activity, education, developing environment, quality of education, content, development.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье можно увидеть анализ повседневной деятельности дошкольных образовательных организаций, то есть выполняемой ими работы в течение дня, и с помощью каких методов происходит прививание детям понятий национальной ценности.*

Ключевые слова: *фронтальный, ценностный, Национальный, центры развития, деятельность, образование, программа, образовательная деятельность, образование, развивающая среда, качество образования, содержание, развитие.*

In the "Ilk Qadam" state curriculum, educational activities are based on the group's daily routine, and daily activities planned by the pedagogue are reflected in it. Children's games, free time and educational activities are carried out alternately. The main content of the developmental environment organized in the group is determined by the fact that it should be rich in cultural-historical values, national

and regional traditions, nature and climatic features, form the basics of the child's primary worldview, and help the child's successful social adaptation.

If we analyze the daily activities of pre-school educational organizations, i.e., the work they do during the day, we will see in which ways and methods national values are instilled in children.

Morning hours: the teacher greets each child with a smile, treats him warmly, invites him to play with his friends, talks on various topics are conducted, based on which the children learn about the surrounding people, objects, natural phenomena, and the nature in the area where they live. their affections are cultivated.

In frontal training: although training hours are given in the "First Step" state curriculum, each hour does not have specific topics. In the process of working with the frontal, i.e. general group, the topics are taken based on the topics of the week given for the development centers. The choice of topics is left to the creative approach of educators themselves. With this, it is determined that each preschool educational organization will create its own work program. One of the requirements for the creation of working programs is to familiarize with national values, national treasures, historical monuments, and great people in one's territory. Therefore, the subjects of frontal training are aimed at forming the concepts of national values in children.

Development centers: in these development centers, when we open the topic of 9 months given in the program, we see that in each month there are different topics that call for nationalism and national education. That is, in September, under the theme "Uzbekistan is my Motherland", in October through the theme of "Autumn colors", if they are introduced to the nature of our country, seasonal changes, national treasures, fertile lands, and the labor of farmers, in November, professions will be cultivated. children are given an understanding of how to find joy, and at the same time, by teaching traffic rules, maintaining community order, interest in the work of adults, and respect for professions are brought up from childhood. In

December, health, a healthy lifestyle, sports competitions, organization of New Year tree holidays, holiday impressions, in January through the events of Defender of the Fatherland Day, neighboring countries, in February, great figures of Uzbekistan, in March It became known that children are inculcated with national values through the Navroz holiday and the theme of "Day of Remembrance and Appreciation" in May. In addition, "Preschool education standard", "State requirements for the development of elementary and preschool children of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and We would like to dwell on the scope and summary of the "First Step" state curriculum.

"Speech Cultivation", which is considered one of the main activities in the preschool education organization, also teaches children to be patriotic through national values. It is one of the main factors that educates a person. This training is taught from the moment the child arrives at the educational organization until he graduates from the organization.

In the "Ilk Kadam" state educational program, for children of preparatory school age, a total of 36 hours of "Speech development" training, 72 hours of "Acquainting with my surroundings", "Acquainting with nature", "Fiction with 18 hours were given to "introduction" classes. But we can see that the state curriculum does not provide topics for these classes.

Above, we got acquainted with the hours allocated in the state curriculum for the classes "Speech development", "Environment introduction", "Nature introduction", "Fiction literature".

In the process of familiarization, it was found that the topics for frontal exercises are not given in the state curriculum, the topics are given in the development centers, and although they are given, there are insufficient methodological guides and recommendations for pedagogues to convey them to the child's mind. At the same time, it was found that the topics given to children in the

development centers to form the concepts of national values are insufficient for them to receive enough information on the formation of national values.

In particular, the topics "Uzbekistan", "Motherland", "My city", "Great figures", "Day of defenders of the motherland", "National crafts", "Family" are introduced in all age groups, but observations have shown that the theme is progression from simple to complex is not fully ensured. The homogeneity of the information received from the Internet by educators working in different age groups, and the fact that they are conveyed to children without simplification, indicates that the age characteristics of children are not taken into account.

Our next task is to analyze the significance of these topics in the education of faith in the homeland through examples of national values: fairy tales, proverbs, legends, epics, proverbs, folk tales. In this regard, while studying the program and methodological manuals published on the basis of it, taking into account the fact that national values can be an important source in raising children of school age in the spirit of faith in the motherland in the development center "Til and Speech", how can proverbs in the spirit of national values be used? we paid attention to whether a place was given. In the "Language and speech" center of the group of children of preparatory school age, there are materials related to national values, including proverbs, along with texts and poems on the topic. For example, in the development center of the preparatory group for school, the following proverbs are presented based on the theme "Uzbekistan - my country":

You have a homeland - you have happiness,

The throne of the hard worker.

Your country is peaceful - you are peaceful.

Mother Earth's soil is as precious as mother's milk.

Or after the fairy tale "Sixty Gas Rope" there is a proverb:
If there is work for the head of the country, the husband is now.

The main purpose of the use of these proverbs is to introduce children of the preparatory school age to examples of national values, to show the wisdom of the Uzbek people through them, and to inform them of the experiences they have accumulated throughout their lives. The main thing is to adhere to the ideas of national value put forward in these proverbs. Often, the proverbs given in the training are given at the end of the topic for memorization, the reason for this is that the proverbs serve to complete the topic and are also important for summarizing the ideas expressed in the topic. For example, the function of the proverb given after the above fairy tale "Altmish Gaz Arkon" is important for completing and summarizing the content of the fairy tale, as well as to warn children about faith in the motherland and the need for young men to be ready to protect the motherland.

As we continue to analyze the activities in the "Development Centers", we see that pictures, cards and audio recordings, and educational games are given a large place to the examples of national values.

Uzbek folk tales are one of the sources of educating school-age children in the spirit of faith in the motherland. As we said above, a lot of work has been done to restore folk tales and include them in training, and they are being further improved. At present, many small fairy tales suitable for the mentality and education of children of the preparatory school age have been published.

In the fairy tale "Altmish gaz arkon", which we mentioned above in the analysis of proverbs, the responsibility of everyone for the protection of the homeland is emphasized, but the person who escapes from the protection of the homeland is condemned by the old woman. the whole country will be freed from the enemy simply because of the old woman's entrepreneurship. It is told like a fairy

tale: - "In ancient times, a monster invaded the land. Everyone's work was left at work, and the people of the country rushed to the battlefield for the defense of the homeland. An old woman lived with her only son on the outskirts of the city. The old woman, who found out that the country was flooded, hastily woke up her sleeping son. A vigilant boy is in a hurry to defend his country. The old woman took the only pillow from her bed and began to sow. He took out the wool and made a rope from it. When the rope was sixty yards long, the neighbor looked from behind the wall:

- Hey neighbor, stop, let's run. "Yov is getting closer," he said.

The old woman's face rose to the sky.

- Why don't we run away to the black earth, neighbor! Did you say that shamelessly! If he's close, let's go and shave his beard one by one! - he said and went down the road holding the rope. The neighbor's Ori also came and followed the old woman.

He reached an agreement with the old woman on the neighboring battlefield. They saw that he had climbed the mountain and was throwing stones at the people of the city. The old woman's son climbed a peak and took it. While he was looking for a way to bring other young men to the top, the old woman's eyes fell on her son. The old woman's heart burned like grass. He climbed a big plane tree with a rope in his hand. He threw the rope towards his son. The son quickly grabbed the rope and tied one end of the rope to the peak. He handed the other end to his neighbor. The old woman ordered her neighbor to hang himself on the rope. Two women are hanging from one end of the rope. In an instant, the people below climbed the mountain by climbing the rope. The battle is heating up on the mountain. The inhabitants of the city won over the enemy. The whole nation was grateful to the old woman."

Through such fairy tales, children of school age learn about the wisdom of the Uzbek people, that they do not spare their lives for the sake of the country, the

condemnation of a person who flees from the protection of the country, and that it is everyone's duty to protect the country. At the same time, they also have a desire, desire and aspiration to become the owner of the above qualities. Most importantly, this tale glorifies the figure of a person who believes in the motherland.

Today, the task of the science of pedagogy is to study folklore more deeply and successfully apply it in the educational process. Analyzing the samples of folk oral creativity, which are part of our national values, we would like to emphasize that their influence on educating school-age children in the spirit of faith in the motherland is huge.

Considering the predominance of morality in Eastern education, based on the idea that it is necessary to give knowledge to the children of preschool education organizations in educational activities, trainings, development centers, round talks, "Supporting the development of elementary and preschool children of the Republic of Uzbekistan state requirements", "First Step" state curriculum, "Thematic planning of the educational process in preschool educational institutions" approved and recommended for publication by the decision of the board meeting No. 4 on July 7, 2018 manual was published, in addition, in Appendix 6 of the Decision PQ-5040 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 26, 2021 "On Measures to Fundamentally Improve the System of Spiritual and Educational Affairs" "The history of our national state, the wealth of our great ancestors" among the students and pedagogic staff of educational organizations to develop joint programs, "road map", "My contribution to the development of the country" was determined. "Spirituality Corner" and "National Value Corner" have been established in all preschool educational organizations of our republic, where children are equipped with pictures, books, exhibits, and compositions typical of our nation that call to national value. If we dwell on the subjects of the homeland, which are presented in the training programs, and the resources that serve to educate faith in the homeland, which are shown in the educational program of preschool educational organizations,

it is clear from our analysis that the program and in the manual "Thematic planning of the educational process in pre-school educational institutions", the topics of introduction to Uzbekistan are given during the school year, and this is "My beloved Uzbekistan", " My city, my neighborhood", "Me and my family", "Defenders of the Fatherland Day", "Great figures of Uzbekistan" topics. In the topics, the brief purpose of the homeland, national value, love of the homeland and other concepts is given. But if we take into account the potential of pedagogues, we can see that these topics are not fully conveyed to the child's mind.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Sh.M. Mirziyoev "We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people." - T., Uzbekistan, 2017.-488p.
2. Sh.M. Mirziyoev "Together we will build a free and prosperous, democratic state of Uzbekistan." - T., Uzbekistan, 2016.-56p.
3. Resolution No. 369 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 10, 2020 "On measures to further increase the effectiveness of the work of educating young people in the spirit of national values"
4. Decision PQ-5040 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 26, 2021 "On measures to radically improve the system of spiritual and educational affairs"
5. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - T.: Uzbekistan, 1998-47 p.
6. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education". A perfect generation is the foundation of Uzbekistan's development. - T.: 1998, pp. 20-29.
7. Abdullah Avloni. Turkish culture and morality.-T.:Pedagog,1992.-160 p.
8. Abdullaev M.A. Basics of culture. - Ferghana: 1998.- 179 p.
9. Abdullaev M.A. Problems of national independence and enlightenment. -T.: Science, 1992.- 62 p.
10. Abdullaev K., Yusupov M., Rahmonbekova S. Protocol. (2nd grade exercise).-T.: Uzbekistan, 2006.

11. Juraeva, N. T. (2022). Organization of the educational process in preschool educational organizations. Results of National Scientific Research International Journal, 1(6), 244-251.

12. Aliev A. Spirituality, value and culture: (Fathers of the Motherland).- T.: Academy, 2000.- 630 p.

13. Tuychieva. T. The place of customs and traditions in the system of Uzbek spiritual values. PFN science. narrow Write to get.diss. TDPU in the name of Nizomi.- T., 2000.- 73 p.

14. Tolenov J. The philosophy of values. - T.: Uzbekistan, 1998. - 335 p.

15. Omar Khayyam. Navroznama.- T.: Mehnat, 1990.- 77 p.

16. "First Step" state curriculum - 2022